

Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and Bibliometrics VOSviewer

Riska Febriyanti, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia

wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis techniques by mapping research topics around Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional based on journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 6 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Savings/deposit products; and (6) Other issues. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional, both those which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

Banks are institutions that people trust to store funds safely. Usually, banks have a dual role, namely as collectors and distributors of funds for people who need funds to meet their needs. Banks are also known as financial depository institutions (Nofinawati, 2018).

In Indonesia, banks are divided into Conventional Banks and Sharia Banks. Conventional Banks carry out their activities conventionally and consist of Conventional Commercial Banks and Rural Credit Banks (OJK, 2017). Meanwhile, Sharia Banks carry out their activities based on sharia principles, and consist of Sharia Commercial Banks and Sharia Rural Banks. (Niatuzzahra, 2018).

One of the banks in Indonesia is Bank Panin, which has a Sharia Business Unit, namely Bank Panin Dubai Syariah. Bank Panin has carried out an Initial Public Offering (IPO), while Bank Panin Dubai Syariah has carried out an IPO, which is usually called going public on January 15 2014. Before carrying out the IPO, Bank Panin Dubai Syariah had experienced quite rapid growth. Bank Panin Dubai Syariah has also offered shares to the public and listed its shares on the Indonesian Stock Exchange (BEI) (Kurnia, 2020).

The discussions or scientific publications regarding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional continue to increase every year. Based on the Garuda website (Garuda Reference Digital), from 2012 to 2022 there have been 93 journals published.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional uses library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional, both those which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

PT Bank Panin Tbk is a banking company in Indonesia which was founded on 17 August 1971 based on Deed No. 85 in front of a Notary in Jakarta with the names Bank Industri Djaja Indonesia, Bank Kemakmuran, Bank Industri dan Dagang Indonesia. Meanwhile, Bank Panin Dubai Syariah was founded on January 8 1972 based on the Limited Bank Company Deed Number 12 by Notary Moeslim Dalid in Malang City with the initial name PT Bank Pasar Bersaudara Djaja (Nur Azizah, 2019). Then on 6 October 2009, based on the Decree of the Governor of Bank Indonesia Number 11/52/KEP.GBI/DpG/2009, Bank Panin Dubai Syariah was designated as a commercial bank based on sharia principles and began operating on 2 December 2009 (Lusitania, 2018).

Sharia financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit riba (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Sharia financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of sharia financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Sharia financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, sharia financial inclusion also supports the development of the sharia financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research. The research object is Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Bank Panin Dubai originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Bank Panin Dubai " for the entire year period (2012 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the

number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings and research space based on library research (Budianto, 2022) .

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional

The results of a search for article publications on the Garuda website (Digital Referral Garba) regarding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional from 2012 to 2022 show that 92 journals have been published. The number of Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional research publications continues to increase every year. 2021 will be the year with the highest number of publications, namely 18 articles. This figure is the highest number of publications in 10 years. The average number of article publications regarding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional is 9 articles per year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2012	1	2018	9
2013	3	2019	17
2014	4	2020	14
2015	4	2021	18
2016	11	2022	3
2017	8		
Total 92			

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, there is data on the names of affiliates/institutions with the number of publications related to Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional research. ACCOUNTING JOURNAL is the affiliate/institution that publishes the most research, namely 3 journals regarding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional.

Table 2. Affiliates/institutions publishing journals regarding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
ACCOUNTING JOURNAL	3
AL-MASHARIF: JOURNAL OF ECONOMIC AND ISLAMIC SCIENCES, AT-TAWASSUTH: Journal of Islamic Economics, Journal of Applied Islamic Economics and Finance, Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sharia Economics, Student Online Journal (JOM) in the Field of Economics	2

AkMen SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL, Aksara Public, Al-Adl: Legal Journal, Al-bank: Journal of Islamic Banking and Finance, Al-Mashrafiyah (Journal of Sharia Economics, Finance and Banking), AL-MUZARA'AH, AMWALUNA (Journal of Economics and Finance Syariah), Ar-Ribh: Journal of Islamic Economics, CALYPTRA, Dinar: Journal of Sharia Economics Study Program, Diponegoro Journal of Islamic Economics and Business, EKSISBANK (Sharia Economics and Banking Business), Expansion: Journal of Economics, Finance, Banking and Accounting, Equator Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship (EJME), FINANSIA: Journal of Accounting and Sharia Banking, I-Finance Journal, Indicator: Scientific Journal of Management and Business, International Journal of Business Studies, INVOICE: JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING SCIENCE, IQTISHODUNA, JBMP (Jurnal of Business, Management and Banking), JKBM (JOURNAL OF BUSINESS CONCEPTS AND MANAGEMENT), J-MAS (Journal of Management and Science), JMK (Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship), Journal of Engineering, Technology, and Applied Science, Journal of Management Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), Journal of World Conference (JWC), JSMA, Journal of Business Administration, JOURNAL OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION (JAB), Journal of Accounting, Journal of Actual Accounting, JOURNAL OF BUSINESS AND DEVELOPMENT, Journal of Ekonika: Economic Journal of Kadiri University, Journal of Business Economics and Entrepreneurship, Journal of Economics and Business (EK&BI), JOURNAL OF ISLAMIC ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS, JOURNAL OF ECONOMICS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP, Indonesian Journal of Economics and Statistics, Journal of Effective Economics, Journal of Trend Economics, Journal of Economics: Management, Accounting and Sharia Banking, EMPATHY Journal, EDUNOMIKA SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL, Scientific Journal of Islamic Economics, FEB Student Scientific Journal, M-PROGRESS SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL, Journal of Business Administration Science, Journal of Accounting and Sharia Business (AKSY), Journal of Justisia Ekonomika: Master of Sharia Economic Law, Journal of Business Management and Entrepreneurship, Journal of Management Update, Mantik Penusa Journal, Masharif al-Syariah Journal: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Student Online Journal (JOM) in the Field of Social Sciences and Political Sciences, Capital Markets and Business Journal, Private Law Journal, Pseudocode Journal, Malahayati Accounting and Management Research Journal, MANAGEMENT & ACCOUNTING RESEARCH

1

JOURNAL, JWM (JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT INSIGHTS), Channel: Journal of Communication Science, KREATIF: Scientific Journal of Pamulang University Management Study Program, Li Falah: Journal of Islamic Economics and Business Studies, Mabny: Journal of Sharia Management and Business, MAGMA: JURNAL MAGISTER OF MANAGEMENT, MAJALAH SCIENCE METHODODA, Operations Excellence: Journal of Applied Industrial Engineering, Owner: Research and Journal of Accounting, PANTUN, PARADIGMA: JOURNAL OF RELIGIOUS SCIENCE AND CULTURE, Communication Perspective: Journal of Political Communication and Business Communication, POINT: Journal of Economics and Management, SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF REFLECTION: Economic, Accounting, Management and Business, SEGMENT Journal of Management and Business, SULTANIST: Journal of Management and Finance, Business Studies, USU LAW JOURNAL, Face of Law

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

Furthermore, all researchers only wrote 1 journal article about Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional. They are: Abdilah, Fani Firmansyah, Kotijah Fadilah, Afriani Ina, Raden Irna, Khodijah, Aini, Fitrotu, Aini, Salamiah, Iwan Riswandie, Muhammad, Amanda, Ismaulina Ismaulina, Juliana Putri, Amidy, Rizal Ma'ruf, Ananda R, Risti Dwi Ramasari, Erlina Erlina, Andriani A, Permatasari, Anjarsari, Novian, Annisa, Amanda, Annisa D, Isfandayani, Arimbawa, Modis April Shela, I Gede, Ascarya, Dina Wening Ati Dianti, Irfan Syauqi Beik, Azzahroh, Asma, Barnas, Benny, Basri, Deviantika Fahriza, Early Ridho Kismawadi, Daryanto, Wiwiek Mardawiyah, Nabilah Haeronisa, Fifi Afiyanti Triuspitorini, Dewi Rani Putri Kusuma, Dewi, Toman Romanco, Sormin, Anisah, Dimyati, Dadang, Dr. Siwi Dyah Ratnasari SE. MM., SE MM., Dr. Rina Rahmawati, Early Ridho Kismawadi, Uun Dwi Al Muddatstsir, Firda Azkiya Safitri, Fatoni, Normalisa, Ahmad Fikri Zulfikar, Febrianti, Silfia, Dian Filianti, Dhevy Ulinnuha Sholichah, Gunawan, R, Guspendri, Revi Candra, Nasfizar, Harahap, Aderina K, Harras, Hadyati, Harsono, Mochamad Syaifudin Al Azis, Haryani, Fitriani D, Heriyanto, Indayang, Efendi, Marisi Butarbutar, Darwin Lie, Irwansyah, Saladin Ghalib, Dora Vicky Permatasari, Ismawati, Istiqomah, Sudarwati Sudarwati, Windy Helena, Kartika Dheana, Kasmiruddin, Devia Armawati, Khunaifi, Robbah, Louis Daulat, Yetty Prawiro, Lubis, Anggia Sari, Luhur, Raden Yohanes, Mahesa, Gema, Makatita, Reyner F, Mangindaan, Areros Joannes, Pongoh, Marcella, Ollie, Megawaty, Muharam, Hari, Mulazid, Erik Rifad Hendra Putra, Ade Sofyan, Nafisah, Supriyono, Nawati, Nofi, Ningsih Dani, Dewita Suryati, Samsir, Ningsih, Asyraf Mustamin, Tri Mulato, Supriadi, Nugraha, Muhammad Ega, Nurdin, Rizka H, Ruhadi, Nurjanah, Gina, Oktavianto, Rizky Arief, Pasaribu, Ananda Anugrah Nasution, M Fauzan, Pradesyah R, Pujiyono, Donny Eka S, Arif, Purwanti, Qodriyah, Topan Perkasa H, Aminh S, Ridwansyah, Taufiq R, Rimawan, Irwan M, Rochmaniah, Afina R, Rosmini A, Suarni, Saifullah, Firdaus, Imam F, Santoso, Arief Budi, Satria, Edia, Sepianingrum, Elisa, Septiarini, Firly Aulia Alhimnie, Dina Fitriisia, Sijaga, Rokhmah Mutakhidah, Yacobo P, Silitonga Ando Fahda Aulia, Selfia Karolina, Simarmata, Henry Dunan Pardede, Hengki Mangiring Parulian, Sitio, Vera

Sylvia Saragi, Sormin, Jessica Puji Astuti, Partogian, Steven Unika, Prihatsanti, Stiawan Vivi Esty Magfiroh, Evan, M Sulaiman, Cici A, Suryoko A, Nugraha S, Hari S, Sutarno, Syafriansyah, Hasdiana S, Muhammad, Syah, Ardy Firman, Tampubolon Utari Maharany Barus, Hasim Purba, Sunarmi Sunarmi, Wahyu Simon, Taradipa, Putri Seyla, Utami Intan Puspitasari, Esti Margiyanti, Verianto H, Wahyuni, Sahrullah, Widuri, Trisnia, Yuliansyah, Hendy, Yusa Julia, Mochammad, Zahro, Masyrifah.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional

Based on search results on the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) regarding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional research publications, 92 articles were obtained. Next, the article is downloaded in RIS (Research Information Systems) format then input into VOSViewer software and analyzed. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional

Source: Processed data, VOSViewer 1.6.18 software

topics were obtained, as in Figure 1 above. The results are as follows:

- Cluster 1. Red, consists of 28 topics, namely: according, application, article, banking institution, benefit, cash flow, community, consumer, credit agreement, creditor, customer campaign, customer decision, debtor, document, fund, independent variable, interview, interview technique, loss, marketing mix, regulation, safe deposit box, saving, sharia cash flow statement, significance level, significant influence, strategy, SWOT analysis.
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 27 topics, namely: analytical technique, camels, capital, capital adequacy ratio, car, comparison, credit, deposit ratio, descriptive analysis, difference, financial

performance, gcg, good corporate governance, government, important role, income, initial public offering, npf, npl, performing financing, public, revenue, rgec method, risk, risk management, risk profile, significant difference.

- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 25 topics, namely: business strategy, covid, data analysis technique, documentation, dominant influence, earnings, end, eps, equity, granger causality test, gross domestic product, idx, increase, mean, mudaraba deposit, murabahah financing, net income, net profit, net profit margin, pandemic, PT Bank Panin Dubai Syariah, share, stock price, stock price performance, time deposit.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 15 topics, namely: beta coefficient, department collection personal loan pt, employee, employee, employee best, path analysis, productivity, research sample, significant negative effect, significance, significant on work morale employees at PT Bank Panin Palu branch, technology, work environment work motivation, workplace deviance.
- Cluster 5. Purple consists of 14 topics, namely: career development, decision process, employee performance, employees knowledge sharing, management audit, organizational commitment, primary data, questionnaire, respondents, revenue sharing, significant value, t count, t table value, training.
- Cluster 6. Light blue consists of 10 topics, namely: competency, employee performance, fraud, independence, internal auditor, job rotation, organizational culture, professionalism, purposive sampling method, significant effect.
- Cluster 7. The color orange consists of 9 topics, namely: closeness, correlation coefficient, job satisfaction, organizational citizenship, relationship, sampling technique, situational leadership, study population, transformational leaders.
- Cluster 8. The dark red color consists of 9 topics, namely: brand image, characteristics, commitment, customer loyalty, customer satisfaction, customer value, loyalty, satisfaction, service quality.
- Cluster 9. Light purple consists of 8 topics, namely: data envelopment analysis, efficiency, extent, inefficiency, measurement, merger, object, researcher.
- Cluster 10. The pink color consists of 7 topics, namely: credit card, information, information system, credit, credit and, process, system.
- Cluster 11. The light green color consists of 4 topics, namely: mudharabah financing, musyarakah financing, pt bank panin syariah tbk, total assets.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Financial Performance of Bank Panin Dubai

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 23 topics related to the financial performance of Bank Panin Dubai, namely:

1. First, the influence of credit, operational expenses, Non-Performing Loans/NPL on capital.
2. Second, the influence of Bank Panin Syariah's contribution to the total net profit of Bank Panin Conventional.

3. Third, the influence of the rupiah exchange rate, liquidity, leverage, profitability, financial performance, total sales and net profit on share price performance.
4. Fourth, stock performance is based on stock beta and Market Value Added/MVA.
5. Fifth, analysis of abnormal returns on company shares.
6. Sixth, control of the online financial information system in the transaction process.
7. Seventh, predict financial distress and bankruptcy with the Altman Z-Score and Grover O-Score methods.
8. Eighth, the influence of profitability, Murabahah financing, receivable income, and company size on Return On Assets/ROA.
9. Ninth, the influence of Go Public/IPO on company performance, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Return On Assets/ROA, Non Performing Financing/NPF, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR.
10. Tenth, cash flow financial reports according to sharia.
11. Eleventh, the influence of Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing on total assets.
12. Twelfth, comparison of financial ratios between conventional and sharia banks.
13. Thirteenth, analysis of Non Performing Loans/NPL.
14. Fourteenth, the influence of profitability on profit growth.
15. Fifteenth, financial performance uses Risk-Based Bank Rating/RBBR, DuPont System analysis and Risk Profile.
16. Sixteenth, distribution of profits in sharia accounting to achieve the principle of justice.
17. Seventeenth, bank health level using the RGEC and CAMEL methods.
18. Eighteenth, profitability level using the ARDL-ECM method.
19. Nineteenth, the influence of macroeconomics on stock returns.
20. Twentieth, the influence of Murabahah, Musyarakah and Mudharabah financing on profitability.
21. Twenty-first, the influence of leverage, disclosure of Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR, and profitability on company value.
22. Twenty-second, measuring company efficiency uses financial ratios with the Data Envelopment Analysis/DEA approach.
23. Twenty-third, the influence of capital profitability and liquidity on financial performance.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Panin Dubai Employee Performance

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 30 topics related to the performance of Bank Panin Dubai employees, namely:

1. Management audit.
2. Sharing knowledge.
3. Organizational culture.
4. Work discipline.
5. Self-efficacy.
6. Facility.
7. Intensive.
8. Job satisfaction.
9. Situational and transformational leadership.

10. Organizational commitment.
11. Communication.
12. Trust.
13. Compensation.
14. Work environment.
15. Locus of control of marketer employees.
16. Employee relations management.
17. Work motivation.
18. Narcissism.
19. Organizational Citizenship Behavior/OCB.
20. Training.
21. Employee placement.
22. Career development.
23. Punishment.
24. Internal control.
25. Best employee award.
26. Recruitment.
27. Rewards.
28. Resilience with work engagement.
29. Work stress.
30. Level of education.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Customer Behavior at Bank Panin Dubai

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 21 topics related to the behavior of Bank Panin Dubai customers, namely:

1. Profit sharing.
2. Brand image and attitude.
3. Customer delivered value.
4. Price.
5. Social identity.
6. Religious advertising.
7. Characteristics.
8. Satisfaction.
9. Service quality.
10. Trust.
11. Commitment.
12. Communication.
13. Mobile banking services use SWOT.
14. Location.
15. Mark.
16. Promotion.
17. Product.
18. Handling complaints/problems.
19. Company reputation.
20. Service recovery.
21. Customer relations strategy.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Panin Dubai Bank Financing/Credit Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 4 research topics related to Bank Panin Dubai financing products, namely:

1. First, the difference in the method of providing credit to conventional banks and Murabahah financing.
2. Second, the mechanism and problems of Mudharabah financing.
3. Third, implementing alternative Hajj and Umrah financing contracts.
4. Fourth, risk mitigation techniques for KPR take over products.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Panin Dubai Bank Savings Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 3 research topics related to Panin Dubai Bank savings/savings products, namely:

1. First, SWOT analysis for marketing fundraising products.
2. Second, the influence of profit sharing levels, share prices, Gross Domestic Product/GDP, BI rate, and inflation on the growth of Mudharabah deposits.
3. Third, implementing the Hajj savings marketing mix.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Other Issues at Bank Panin Dubai

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 6 research topics related to issues at Bank Panin Dubai, namely:

1. First, customer protection for storing goods in a safe deposit box.
2. Second, the bank's responsibility in the safe deposit box rental agreement which contains an exoneration clause.
3. Third, execution of fiduciary guarantees.
4. Fourth, the influence of independence, competence and professionalism of internal auditors on the ability to detect fraud.
5. Fifth, resolving disputes over customer SHM ownership auction lawsuits.
6. Sixth, ZIS fund management linkage program.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 6 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Bank Panin Dubai Sharia and Conventional, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Savings/deposit products; and (6) Other issues.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada

- Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar*

quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>

- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni*, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>